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**“GLOBAL RAQAMLI INTEGRATSIYALASHUV:
2030-YILGACHA YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISHDA
TEXNOLOGIK VA INDUSTRIAL SANOATNI RIVOJLANTIRISH
ORQALI MIKRO VA MAKROIQTISODIY BARQAROR
O'SISHNI TA'MINLASH DOLZARBLIGI”**

**“GLOBAL DIGITAL INTEGRATION: THE RELEVANCE OF
ENSURING MICRO AND MACROECONOMIC SUSTAINABLE
GROWTH THROUGH TECHNOLOGICAL AND INDUSTRIAL
DEVELOPMENT IN THE TRANSITION TO A GREEN
ECONOMY BY 2030”**

**«ГЛОБАЛЬНАЯ ЦИФРОВАЯ ИНТЕГРАЦИЯ:
АКТУАЛЬНОСТЬ ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЯ УСТОЙЧИВОГО
МИКРО- И МАКРОЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО РОСТА ЧЕРЕЗ
РАЗВИТИЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ И ИНДУСТРИАЛЬНОЙ
ПРОМЫШЛЕННОСТИ В ПЕРЕХОДЕ К ЗЕЛЁНОЙ
ЭКОНОМИКЕ К 2030 ГОДУ»**

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- 05.01.00 – Axborot texnologiyalari, boshqaruv va kompyuter grafikasi
- 05.01.01 – Muhandislik geometriyasi va kompyuter grafikasi. Audio va video texnologiyalari
- 05.01.02 – Tizimli tahlil, boshqaruv va axborotni qayta ishlash
- 05.01.03 – Informatikaning nazariy asoslari
- 05.01.04 – Hisoblash mashinalari, majmualari va kompyuter tarmoqlarining matematik va dasturiy ta'minoti
- 05.01.05 – Axborotlarni himoyalash usullari va tizimlari. Axborot xavfsizligi
- 05.01.06 – Hisoblash texnikasi va boshqaruv tizimlarining elementlari va qurilmalari
- 05.01.07 – Matematik modellashtirish
- 05.01.11 – Raqamli texnologiyalar va sun'iy intellekt
- 05.02.00 – Mashinasozlik va mashinashunoslik
- 05.02.08 – Yer usti majmualari va uchish apparatlari
- 05.03.02 – Metrologiya va metrologiya ta'minoti
- 05.04.01 – Telekommunikatsiya va kompyuter tizimlari, telekommunikatsiya tarmoqlari va qurilmalari. Axborotlarni taqsimlash
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- 05.05.05 – Issiqlik texnikasining nazariy asoslari
- 05.05.06 – Qayta tiklanadigan energiya turlari asosidagi energiya qurilmalari
- 05.06.01 – To'qimachilik va yengil sanoat ishlab chiqarishlari materialshunosligi
- 05.08.03 – Temir yo'l transportini ishlatish
- 05.09.01 – Qurilish konstruksiyalari, bino va inshootlar
- 05.09.04 – Suv ta'minoti. Kanalizatsiya. Suv havzalarini muhofazalovchi qurilish tizimlari
- 10.00.06 – Qiyosiy adabiyotshunoslik, chog'ishtirma tilshunoslik va tarjimashunoslik
- 10.00.04 – Yevropa, Amerika va Avstraliya xalqlari tili va adabiyoti
- 08.00.01 – Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 – Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 – Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 – Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
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- 08.00.06 – Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 – Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
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- 08.00.09 – Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 – Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 – Marketing
- 08.00.12 – Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 – Menejment
- 08.00.14 – Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 – Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 – Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 – Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

Ma'lumot uchun, OAK
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IMPROVING THE ECONOMIC POTENTIAL OF OIL AND GAS INDUSTRY ENTERPRISES IN
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IMPROVING THE ECONOMIC POTENTIAL OF OIL AND GAS INDUSTRY ENTERPRISES IN UZBEKISTAN: MODERN CHALLENGES AND DEVELOPMENT PROSPECTS

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Abstract. The oil and gas industry remains one of the important sectors of Uzbekistan's economy, ensuring energy security, industrial growth, and sustainable economic development. Under the conditions of increasing global competition, technological transformation, and changes in the international energy market, improving the economic potential of oil and gas industry enterprises has become one of the important areas of industrial development. This paper examines the major factors affecting the economic potential of oil and gas enterprises, including investment activity, technological modernization, corporate governance, innovation, and digital transformation. Particular attention is paid to the current reforms implemented in Uzbekistan aimed at increasing production efficiency and strengthening the competitiveness of industrial enterprises.

Keywords: oil and gas industry, economic potential, industrial enterprises, investment, innovation, digitalization, competitiveness, sustainable development, Uzbekistan.

Annotatsiya. Neft-gaz sanoati O'zbekiston iqtisodiyotining muhim tarmoqlaridan biri bo'lib, energiya xavfsizligi, sanoat o'sishi va barqaror iqtisodiy rivojlanishni ta'minlashda muhim o'rin egallaydi. Global raqobatning kuchayishi, texnologik transformatsiya va xalqaro energiya bozoridagi o'zgarishlar sharoitida neft-gaz sanoati korxonalarining iqtisodiy salohiyatini oshirish sanoat rivojlanishining muhim yo'nalishlaridan biriga aylangan. Mazkur maqolada neft-gaz korxonalarining iqtisodiy salohiyatiga ta'sir etuvchi asosiy omillar, jumladan, investitsiya faolligi, texnologik modernizatsiya, korporativ boshqaruv, innovatsiyalar va raqamli transformatsiya masalalari ko'rib chiqilgan. O'zbekistonda ishlab chiqarish samaradorligini oshirish va sanoat korxonalari raqobatbardoshligini mustahkamlashga qaratilgan joriy islohotlarga alohida e'tibor qaratilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: neft-gaz sanoati, iqtisodiy salohiyat, sanoat korxonalari, investitsiya, innovatsiya, raqamlashtirish, raqobatbardoshlik, barqaror rivojlanish, O'zbekiston.

Аннотация. Нефтегазовая промышленность остаётся одной из важных отраслей экономики Узбекистана, обеспечивающей энергетическую безопасность, промышленный рост и устойчивое экономическое развитие. В условиях усиления глобальной конкуренции, технологической трансформации и изменений на международном энергетическом рынке повышение экономического потенциала предприятий нефтегазовой промышленности стало одним из важных направлений промышленного развития. В данной статье рассматриваются основные факторы, влияющие на экономический потенциал нефтегазовых предприятий, включая инвестиционную активность, технологическую модернизацию, корпоративное управление, инновации и цифровую трансформацию. Особое внимание уделено текущим реформам, реализуемым в Узбекистане и направленным на повышение эффективности производства и укрепление конкурентоспособности промышленных предприятий.

Ключевые слова: нефтегазовая промышленность, экономический потенциал, промышленные предприятия, инвестиции, инновации, цифровизация, конкурентоспособность, устойчивое развитие, Узбекистан.

INTRODUCTION

The oil and gas industry has traditionally occupied a leading position in the economic development of many countries due to its significant contribution to industrial production, energy security, export revenues, and employment. For Uzbekistan, this sector remains one of the most important components of the national economy, providing the energy resources necessary for the functioning of industrial enterprises and supporting sustainable economic growth. In recent years, a number of measures have been implemented to modernize the energy sector, improve investment attractiveness, and increase the efficiency of industrial production..

At the same time, the development of oil and gas industry enterprises is influenced by numerous external and internal factors. Global energy market fluctuations, technological changes, increasing environmental requirements, and growing competition require enterprises to improve management systems and utilize available resources more efficiently. Consequently, enhancing the economic potential of enterprises has become an essential condition for ensuring stable production, financial sustainability, and long-term competitiveness.

Against this background, researchers increasingly emphasize the importance of combining investment policy, innovation, and strategic management in strengthening industrial development. Therefore, the purpose of this thesis is to identify the main directions for improving the economic potential of oil and gas industry enterprises in Uzbekistan and to determine the factors that contribute to their sustainable development under modern economic conditions.

The economic potential of an enterprise represents a complex combination of production, financial, technological, organizational, and human resources that determine its ability to achieve strategic objectives and maintain sustainable competitiveness. In the oil and gas industry, this concept has become increasingly important because enterprises operate in a rapidly changing environment characterized by technological innovation, market uncertainty, and growing investment requirements. Consequently, the effective utilization of available resources plays a decisive role in improving production efficiency and ensuring long-term economic stability.

Furthermore, the experience of developed countries demonstrates that investment in technological modernization significantly increases the competitiveness of oil and gas enterprises. Modern digital technologies, automation systems, and innovative production methods not only improve operational efficiency but also reduce production costs and enhance environmental sustainability. As a result, enterprises become more adaptable to changes in international energy markets and are better prepared to respond to future economic challenges.

The current stage of development of Uzbekistan's oil and gas industry is characterized by the implementation of modernization measures, increased investment activity, and gradual digital transformation. These measures are aimed at improving production efficiency, strengthening corporate governance, and creating favorable conditions for attracting domestic and foreign investment. As a result, the economic potential of oil and gas enterprises increasingly depends not only on the availability of natural resources but also on the efficiency of management, technological capabilities, and innovation capacity.

An equally important factor is the effective allocation of investment resources. International practice shows that enterprises investing in technological renewal, employee training, and digital production management achieve higher productivity and better financial performance. In addition, the introduction of integrated management systems improves operational decision-making and reduces production risks, thereby enhancing the long-term sustainability of enterprises.

The experience of Uzbekistan also confirms the importance of these factors. In recent years, support measures, investment projects, and institutional reforms have contributed to improving the operating environment for oil and gas enterprises. The implementation of modern production technologies, expansion of geological exploration, and modernization of processing facilities have become the main priorities of sectoral development. These measures are expected to improve the competitiveness of the national oil and gas industry and support economic growth.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Improving the economic potential of oil and gas industry enterprises is a key prerequisite for ensuring the sustainable development of Uzbekistan's energy sector. The findings indicate that investment activity, technological modernization, innovation, and effective corporate governance have a significant impact on enterprise performance and competitiveness. At the same time, digital transformation and the efficient use of available resources contribute to increasing productivity and strengthening financial sustainability. Therefore, further development of the oil and gas industry should be based on an integrated approach that combines investment support, technological renewal, and modern management practices. The implementation of these measures may improve the competitiveness of oil and gas enterprises and increase their contribution to the country's long-term economic development.

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